

Are fertilizers and improved seeds complementary or substitute in the process of adoption? Case study of northern Ethiopia

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Agricultural technology is viewed as a means through which agricultural productivity and production improvement can be made in the fight against hunger and poverty. Agricultural extension is one of the policy instruments to stimulate agricultural development through promoting the adoption and diffusion of improved technologies. Despite various extension efforts, the process of adopting modern agricultural inputs is very slow. The main objective of this study was to evaluate the relationship between agricultural inputs and identify factors that influence agricultural technology adoption decision. Data were obtained from MU-IUC socio-economic project farm household survey conducted in (2009/10) agricultural season. A total of 283 farmers from Atsbi and Wukro woreda's were randomly taken to the study. The result revealed that fertilizers and improved seeds were the common technologies used by the farm households. Fertilizers and improved seeds also found to be complementary in the adoption process. Analysis of agricultural technology adoption using logit model indicated that, holding other factors constant, households with larger farm size, owning more animals, access to irrigation and larger proportion of literate family members are more likely to adopt new agricultural technologies. It was suggested that farmers have an incentive to adopt many technologies at once.

Key words: Agricultural technologies, extension, adoption.

INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector is the principal engine of growth of the Ethiopian economy employs 83% of the labor force, contributes about 90% of exports and 45% of gross domestic product (GDP), and provides about 70% of the country's raw material requirement for large-and medium-scale industries (MoARD, 2009).

Agricultural technology is viewed as a means through which agricultural efficiency, productivity and production improvement can be made in the fight against hunger and poverty. The introduction of higher-yielding and or pest/disease varieties of many crops (maize, sorghum, cassava, peanuts, and cashew) and improved inputs (fertilizers, pesticides and irrigation) has enhanced the hope to increase productivity and rural incomes. That hope would remain unrealized if the rate of adoption of proven technologies remains very low. (Morris et al., 2007)

Transforming Ethiopian agriculture from its current subsistence orientation into market orientated production

system forms the basis of the agricultural development strategy of the Government of Ethiopia (GoE). The agricultural extension service is one of the institutional support services that have a central role to play in the transformation process. The government and non-governmental organizations have consistently promoted chemical fertilizer as a yield-augmenting technology. Despite this promotion, chemical fertilizer adoption rates remain very low (Byerlee et al., 2007).

Improved farming technologies such as high yield crop varieties, chemical fertilizers, and irrigation techniques have been central in raising yields in other parts of the world; however, African farmers have been much slower in adopting these new methods. One reason that farmers cite for not adopting the new technologies is a lack of information regarding how to apply the improved inputs (Morris et al., 2007).

With declining farm size, it becomes increasingly difficult to practice traditional soil-fertility restoring

techniques (e.g. fallowing and crop rotation) and maintain households' livelihoods from the land. As noted by (Mulat, 1996), rising population density typically causes a transition from fallow-based systems to permanent cultivation. To maintain yields under such conditions, farmers must add supplementary nutrients using increased quantities of organic and chemical fertilizers. Although the use of fertilizer has increased in Ethiopia in recent years, there is ample evidence that most farmers are not adequately compensating for the loss of soil nutrients caused by more intensive cultivation.

The agricultural sector dominates the country's economy. Yet, its performance has been very dismal and failed to meet the country's food demand. Shrinking farm size, declining agricultural productivity due to natural resource degradation, and low adoption rate of agricultural inputs remain major challenges of the agricultural sector. The national strategy chimes with a widely held view that poverty reduction in Ethiopia is impossible without significant growth in crop yields for major staples, and this requires improving the adoption of fertilizer, improved seeds, chemicals and other inputs. (Samuel, 2006)

Currently the agricultural policy of Ethiopia gives high priority to increasing food production through the promotion of improved production technologies among small holders particularly promoting the adoption of improved seeds, fertilizers and pesticides, being the main food crops through the national extension package. Despite this tremendous government involvement, fertilizer use is however still very low, even compared to the African average. The promotion of improved seeds which are considered as the nucleus of any improvement is even more challenging for the extension system. For instance, only half of farmers participating in PADETES used improved seeds (Samuel, 2006).

The main reasons for the existing structural food insecurity in the country are the low level of technological development, which acts as the principal barrier to the efficient utilization of the country's natural resources, Low yield due to low adoption of improved agricultural technologies and low productive efficiency. The relative efficiency of farmers is also very important because it is a factor for aggregate productivity growth and an influence on income distribution.

In many of the previous studies on technology adoption decisions, several factors that reflect personal, physical, economic, and institutional elements were identified on an ad-hoc basis, and analyzed separately in a single equation model or a joint adoption decision with bivariate simultaneous equation model. From an econometric point of view, a single equation estimation approach could cause bias, inconsistency, and inefficiency in parameter estimates unless it is preceded by an examination of complementarity and substitutability among the technologies with the given data (Greene, 2000).

Most of these studies focus on the decision to adopt a specific technology without explicitly considering other

technologies. An aspect of technology adoption that has received less attention is the extent to which different technologies work well together and are adopted collectively or do not work well together and are adopted separately; or, in economic parlance, the extent to which combinations of technology are complementary or substitutable.

Therefore, the objective of this study was to examine current adoption and intensity level of improved agricultural technologies, to examine complementarity and substitutability among agricultural technologies (improved seed and fertilizer) and to identify major socio-economic and demographic factors that influence the adoption of modern agricultural inputs in the region.

Hypotheses

- Adoption of fertilizer and improved seed are mutually independent.
- Farm households are more likely to use fertilizer and improved seed on irrigated plots than on rain-fed plots.
- Extension Participant farmers use higher rate of modern agricultural inputs than non participants

METHODOLOGY

Data and the study area

The National Regional State of Tigray is one of the National Regional States of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia. It is located in the northern Part of Ethiopia. The economy of Tigray is almost entirely agricultural with small holder cultivation of cereals and pulses mainly characterized by subsistence farming mixed with livestock rearing. Oxen are the only source of traction power and among the main indicators of poverty and inequalities among farmers.

In this study data collected by MU-IUC¹ socio-Economic research project during July and August 2010 is used. The data were gathered through a smallholder farmer questionnaire administered to 283 households with information collected at household member level.

The population for this study consists of small scale farming households of Geba catchment. A three - stage stratified random sampling technique was employed to select the sample for the study.

In the first stage, two woredas² Wukro, and Atsebi representing the four Agroecologies in Tigray region were selected. In the second stage, two tabias³ from each

¹ MU-IUC, an agreement between Mekelle University and VLIR institutional University Cooperation

² Woreda (also spelled wereda) is an administrative division of Ethiopia (managed by a local government), equivalent to a district

woreda were randomly selected. While in the third stage, proportionate random sampling was used to select the farm households.

Model specification

Testing for complementarity and substitutability

Previous studies developed tractable methodology that can show how technologies complement or substitute for each other; in this study a strategy developed by (Yu et al., 2007) to identify the complementarity or substitutability among technology bundles was used.

Yu et al. (2007) derived a method that can distinguish whether a particular pattern of multiple technology adoptions is consistent with mutual independence, mutual substitutability or mutual complementarity. The method follows this logic: Suppose K (K>1) technologies are mutually independent so that adopting one of the technologies does not affect or is not influenced by the presence of any other technologies. The probability of adopting each of K technologies will equal the product of the adoption probabilities of each of the K technologies. In reality, these technologies may be complements or substitutes.

If a set of technologies are mutually complementary, then producers will select that combination of technologies with greater frequency than would occur under the null hypothesis of mutual independence. On the other hand, if the technologies are mutually substitutable for one another, the combination will be bundled together with less frequency than would occur under mutual independence. This strategy is computationally simple and remains feasible even as the number of technologies expands.

If technologies are adopted independently, the production function can be decomposed into technology specific functions. The technology adoption decision can be made independently, ignoring the effects from other technologies usage. However, if technologies are not mutually independently adopted, it cannot be a decompose production function because firms have to incorporate the effects from simultaneous multiple technology adoption, such as economy scales and complemented labor inputs. (Yu et al., 2007)

• Independence test for a specific technology bundle

The null hypothesis (H0) is that K technologies in bundle j are independent. The alternative hypothesis (H1) is two sides: either they are substitutes or they are complements.

H0: The n technologies are mutually independent.

H1: The n technologies are not mutually independent and

may be complements or substitutes.

Each technology adoption decision can be regarded as a Bernoulli trial, a common assumption employed in the single technology adoption literature. Define X_k as a random

Variable which reflects this binary technology adoption decision, X_k has a Bernoulli distribution if:

X_k=1 adopted with probability P_k

X_k=0 not adopted with probability 1-P_k

where 0 ≤ P_k ≤ 1

If technology 1 is independent of technology 2, meaning that its adoption is just as likely whether or not technology 2 is adopted, then the hypothesis

H₀: Pr(X₁ = 1, X₂ = 1) = Pr(X₁ = 1) Pr(X₂ = 1) will be true.

Alternatively, if the adoption of technology 1 changes depending on whether technology 2 is adopted (i.e. there is positive or negative correlation in adoption), then:

(i) Complementary

H₁: Pr(X₁ = 1, X₂ = 1) > Pr(X₁ = 1) Pr(X₂ = 1) or

(ii) Substitute

H₁: Pr(X₁ = 1, X₂ = 1) < Pr(X₁ = 1) Pr(X₂ = 1)

The testing procedure

Independence test for technology bundles done using G test, a log likelihood ratio test of independence, is given by:

$$G = 2 \sum_j^{2k} F^1_j \ln \left(\frac{F^1_j}{F^0_j} \right) \dots\dots\dots 1$$

where F¹_j and F⁰_j are frequency if the technology bundle j observed under H₁ and H₀ respectively.

G is asymptotically distributed as Chi- square with (2K -K- 1) degrees of freedom.

Adoption of improved seeds and fertilizer

In this study, static adoption model approach was used to analyze fertilizer and improved seed adoption by farmers. A static model refers to farmers decisions to adopt an improved technology at a specific place and a specific period of time. This model attempts to answer the question of what determines whether a particular technology is adopted or not and what determines the pattern of adoption at a particular point in time. Adoption commonly refers to the decision to use a new technology or practice by economic units on a regular basis.

A farmer's decision either to adopt or reject a new technology is influenced by the combined effect of a number of factors related to farmers' objectives and constraints. In this study, three aspects were considered

3 Tabia is the lowest administrative unit in the structure of the regional government of Tigray.

in the analysis of factors associated with the adoption of improved varieties and chemical fertilizer:

1. Farmers' socioeconomic circumstances (e.g., age, formal education, etc.)
2. Farmers' resource endowments (e.g., size of family labor, farm size and livestock ownership)
3. Institutional support systems available to farmers (e.g., credit, extension, and availability of inputs).

In adoption studies, responses to a question such as whether a technology was adopted could be yes or no, a typical case of a qualitative dichotomous variable. However, factors (independent variables) that affect a given technology adoption can be expressed both qualitatively and quantitatively.

The Logit multiple regression model containing 9 predictors specified in Equation 2 was regressed against dependent binary variable of technology adoption (TECHADOPT) in order to identify the factors influencing adoption of improved technology.

The empirical model for the adoption of modern agricultural inputs is specified as follows:

$$\text{TECHADOPT} = B_0 + B_1X_1 + B_2X_2 + B_3X_3 + B_4X_4 + B_5X_5 + B_6X_6 + B_7X_7 + B_8X_8 + B_9X_9 + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Equation 2 represents a binary choice model involving the estimation of the probability of adoption of a given technology (Y) as a function of independent variables (X). Where: -TECHADOPT = a dichotomous dependent variable (1 if the farmer adopts either of the two or both technologies, 0 otherwise) β is vector of unknown parameters including constant X_i 's represents the combined effects of the independent variables X_i (see table 1). ε = disturbance term.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics

Family size ranges from 1 to 12 people. The average family size is 5.3 members, which is similar with the regional average of 5.31 and lower than the national average of 6 members (CSA, 2008). Increasing family size especially in rural areas causes the land holding of each household to decrease, which reduces productivity. In the study area about 41% of the respondents had formal education including the traditional education, while 59% of the respondents had no formal education. The result indicates a lower level of literacy among the farmers. Education is a significant factor in facilitating awareness and adoption of agricultural technologies. High literacy levels will enable farmers to understand the intricacies involved in adopting a technology.

About 24.9 percent of the households have access to irrigation. And each house hold uses farm equipments

with the average value of 288 birr. Farmers use local market and Mekelle city as the major trading centre, on average sample respondents have a distance of 7 Km away from local market and 58 Km from Mekelle city with the average quintal transport cost of 18 birr to Mekelle.

Farmers can easily obtain agricultural output, or equivalently seed, sell their products, through market channels if the market functions adequately. Availability of a local market is therefore an incentive for smallholder farmers to increase productivity.

In this study, the average land holding of sample population was found to be 0.7ha with standard deviation of 0.45 ha. This figure is smaller than the national figure, which is 1.2 ha implying relatively less land holding in the study area (CSA, 2008). This is a confirmation that smallholder farmers are operating on a small land holding.

About 15 % of the respondents were within the total income range of 12000-16200 birr, while 76% of them had the average farm income of less than 5000 birr. This indicates that smallholder farmers in the study area operated at merely subsistent level. This low income status has serious deleterious implications on their farm investments and agricultural productivity (Ezeh, 2006).

Current status of adoption of improved agricultural technologies

Agricultural Technology was proxied using variables such as whether the household has used fertilizers, improved seeds, use of mechanization and chemicals. A large number of promising technologies are already available in the region. These include improved varieties (OPV), hybrid seeds and chemical packages, improved on farm storage techniques, methods of small scale irrigation such as treadle pumps and others. Unfortunately, while available in principle, farmers' contact with new technology is distinctly limited in practice. This translates to low rates of technology adoption. Table 2 presents the status of agricultural technology adoption in the region. Seeds are crucial in agriculture. They are one of the most important determinants of productivity. Plant breeding programs in the country have developed and distributed cultivars that aim at increasing efficiency and productivity or maintain productivity in the face of varied agroecologies.

While looking on the adoption status of sample households 33% percent of the respondents adopted improved seed variety, Majority of the farmers (43%) intercropped their plantations with improved varieties. there is also a slight use of pesticide. This was low given that the varieties and technologies have been in existence more than three years.

The sources of information on improved crop technology package available to the farmers included extension workers, fellow farmers/neighbors and mediated information sources. The primary goals of these

Table 1. Description of variables used in logit analysis

Variable	Variable Description
Dependent Variable	
TECHADOP	a dichotomous variable (1 if the farmer adopts either of the two or both technologies, 0 otherwise)
Independent Variables	
X1	access to irrigation(dummy)
X2	farm size in hectare
X3	membership to association (dummy)
X4	literacy ratio
X5	nonfarm income (dummy)
X6	credit other than package loan(dummy)
X7	extension participation (dummy)
X8	animal asset
X9	tabia dummies (barka)
X10	tabia dummy(rubafeleg)

Table 2. Distribution of modern agricultural inputs by woreda.

Technology	Atsbi	Wukro	Total
Fertilizer users	20	55	76
Pesticide users	1	0	1
Improved seed users	17	74	91

Source: own computation

Table 3. Comparison of input use by extension participant and non participant farmers.

Variable	participant(Mean)	Non participant(mean)	T test
Technical efficiency	80	79	-8.5**
Improved seed users	37%	28.7%	-2.21**
Fertilizer users	29.5%	25.3%	-1.69***
Rate of fertilizer use	20	18	-0.6

information sources are to create awareness by diffusing among potential adopters useful and practical information on the innovation and encourage its application. Agricultural extension workers constitute the most important source of information to the farmers as 90% of them obtained information from the extension services. Farmers mentioned a number of constraints that act as deterrents to adoption of improved varieties and technologies. These include: general climate is not suitable, do not have enough land for keeping them and costs of keeping them is too high. These factors also hindered faster rate of adoption.

Intensity of fertilizer utilization

In case of fertilizer used, only 27 % of the sample farmers use fertilizer where 21 % of the total area cultivated is covered by fertilizer. In general fertilizer users tended to use the two major nutrients dap and urea. In addition to the distribution of fertilizer usage, intensity of fertilizer

used in the study area is also important. Results showed that the average fertilizer used was 19.7 kg/ ha which is relatively higher than the 10⁴ kg per hectare average application in Sub-Saharan Africa but much less than the average application in Latin America and South Asia which is nearly 140 kg per hectare. This shows there is a need to focus on the utilization of recommended rate of fertilizers.

Agricultural extension and adoption of agricultural inputs

As part of the agricultural development-led industrialization development strategy, the Ethiopian government introduced the Extension Package Program based on the experiences of the Sasakawa-Global 2000 (SG) project which embarked upon the popularization of

⁴ World Bank data from <http://data.worldbank.org/indicator/AG.CON.FERT.ZS/countries>

large-scale (usually half-hectare) on-farm demonstration plots for already available improved agricultural production technologies. (Alene, 2008)

The package was thus developed against the above backgrounds aiming to improve the Productivity of smallholder farmers through better access to improved production technologies such as fertilizer, improved seeds, pesticides and better cultural practices mainly for cereal crops, including maize, wheat, and teff. The program provided credit, inputs, and extension assistance to participants.

This study investigated the difference in adoption of improved agricultural technologies between extension participants and non participants and the result revealed that extension participants achieve significantly higher percentage of improved seed and fertilizer adoption demonstrating success in facilitating adoption and creating productivity difference. However, the average rate of fertilizer application for extension participants was about 20 kg per hectare, while the nonparticipants had an average rate of 18kg /ha, where the difference in the rate is not statistically significant. The extension package should advocate the usage of the recommended rate of fertilizers.

Examination of complementarity and substitutability

The presence of complementarity and substitutability checked and the two technologies (fertilizers and improved seeds) were found complementary.

As can be seen in table 4 using the probability of adoption for each technology, their relationship was determined using the following criteria developed by (Yu et al, 2007)

(i) Complementary

$$H: \Pr(X_1 = 1, X_2 = 1) > \Pr(X_1 = 1) \Pr(X_2 = 1)$$

$$0.14 > 0.27 * 0.33$$

0.14 > 0.089 implying the presence of complementarity among agricultural technologies.

The G test result for the presence of complementarity using equation 2 calculated to be 12.4 and this value for G test is significant because it exceeds the Chi square value of 6.639 at 1 degree of freedom and critical value of 10%.

This shows that fertilizer and improved seed were complementary in the process of agricultural technology adoption. When technologies are complementary, the productivity of one technology is enhanced by the adoption of the other technologies. This provides an incentive for multiple technology adoption at one production period.

The complementarity among technologies is also contributing to a form of returns to scale that is leading to increasing growth in average farm production. This

finding suggests that farmers have an incentive to adopt combined technologies at once.

Logit analysis of technology adoption

Logit econometric model was used to see the relative influence of different personal, demographic, socio-economic, and institutional variables on adoption of modern agricultural inputs. The result of determinants of adoption of modern agricultural inputs by farmers in the study area is shown in Table 5.

The coefficient of farm-size of farmers was significant at 1 percent and was positive. This shows that the more the size of the farmer's farmland the more is likely to adopt agricultural technology. The size of the family farm is a factor that is often argued as important in affecting adoption decisions. It is frequently argued that farmers with larger farms are more likely to adopt an improved technology (especially modern varieties) compared with those with small farmers as they can afford to devote part of their fields (sometimes the less productive parts) to try out the improved technology. It is also known in the literature that lumpy technologies such as mechanized equipments that require economies of size for it to ensure profitability, there is often a minimum threshold farm size for adoption (e.g. animal traction). (Augustine, 2005)

The literacy ratio of the household members was significant at 5 percent confidence interval and was positive which implies that the larger the household's literacy ratio, which results from large number of literate household members, the higher the probability of adopting improved technologies by farmers. Farmers with higher number of literate family members can easily process information and search for appropriate technologies to alleviate their production constraints.

The coefficient for access to irrigation is positive and significant at 99% confidence interval. Keeping other factors constant irrigation users have higher probability of adopting agricultural technologies than farmers with rain fed agriculture. Higher income that can be generated in irrigated agriculture may motivate the adoption of modern agricultural inputs.

Similarly, livestock ownership (sometimes a proxy for wealth accumulation) is found to positively and significantly influence the adoption decision. The rate of adoption of a new technology is subject to its profitability and the degree of risk and uncertainty associated with it, and is highly influenced by the capital requirement.

Access to extension services and membership to an agricultural association were employed in this analysis to measure the extent to which farm households surveyed are exposed to agricultural information. It was expected as Asfaw and Admassie (2004) that the more exposure to agricultural information the higher the probability of adoption of improved agricultural input or package of technologies. But Access to extension did not

Table 4. Complementarity and substitutability tests

Technology	No.	Percentage
Improved seed	91	33 %
Fertilizer	76	27%
Both (improved seed + Fertilizer)	40	14%

Table 5. Regression estimates of coefficients associated with agricultural technology adoption.

Variable	Coef.	Std. Err
access to irrigation	1.240367***	0.4030926
farm size	0.7295175**	0.3165236
association membership	0.2510673	0.3029087
literacy ratio	1.448586**	0.7088618
nonfarm income	-0.4482329	0.3236237
credit	0.3079663	0.342379
Extension participation	0.0785357	0.3445335
Animal asset	0.2689223***	0.0907089
barka	-.7803478	0.4799395
rubafeleg	-1.01143	0.4815043
adiqsanded	-.2780106	0.4762711
cons	-2.822129***	0.9997022
Log likelihood	-141.09847	
LR chi2	78.80	
Prob > chi2	0.0000	
Pseudo R2	0.2183	

*** = significant at 1 %; ** =significant at 5 %;
Source: own survey

significantly correlate with the decision to adopt improved seeds as indicated in table 5 this lack of a significant link between extension and the adoption of agricultural technologies is potentially worrisome. It is inconsistent with the hypothesis that extension services in agriculture educate farmers about the potential benefits of new agricultural technologies. The insignificant effect of extension services might be indicative that only economic constraints and farmers' perception might be influencing agricultural technology adoption and farmers have good knowledge about agricultural technologies through media and information from neighbours.

Conclusion

The result found fertilizer and improved seed as common technologies used by the farm households. Fertilizer use in the study area was 19.7 kg/ ha. Fertilizers and improved seeds were found to be complementary. Complementarily among technologies is contributing to a form of returns to scale that is leading to increasing growth in average farm production. This finding suggests that farmers have an incentive to adopt many technologies at once. This study identifies that agricultural technology adoption decision is strongly influenced by literacy ratio, access to irrigation, farm size and animal asset.

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